

EFFECTS OF SUSTAINED NATURAL APOPHYSEAL GLIDES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF CERVICAL RADIOCULOPATHY

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ABSTRACT The study examined the effects of Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides (SNAGS) on pain intensity (PI), neck functional disability (NFD) and range of motion (ROM) in patients with cervical radiculopathy (CR).

Sixty-seven patients (male: n = 34, female: n = 33) with cervical radiculopathy were purposively recruited from the Outpatient Physiotherapy Department of the Usman Danfodio University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto for the study. Each subject was treated with cryotherapy for seven minutes, and sustained natural apophyseal glides were administered twice weekly for six weeks. Visual analogue scale, neck disability index questionnaires and inclinometer were used to assess the pain intensity, disability and cervical range of motion respectively pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th week of the treatment session. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data with the alpha level at 0.05. Result showed that there was a significant difference in pain intensity ($F = 521.35$, $p < 0.001$), neck disability ($F = 102.55$, $p < 0.001$) and right side flexion ($F = 16.86$; $p < 0.001$) in 3rd week and 6th week when compared with pretreatment pain intensity.

Therefore, it can be concluded from the study that SNAGS is effective in the management of cervical radiculopathy.

KEYWORDS Cervical, Radiculopathy, Pain intensity, Disability, Range of motion

Introduction

Cervical radiculopathy forms an important subgroup of neck disorders, and although less prevalent than general neck pain, it has been shown to lead to more severe pain and disability [1-6]. The systematic review on cervical radiculopathy by Barrett et al. reported that it is the most impactful population-based study performed in Rochester Minnesota from 1976 – 1990 [7]. The

study estimated the annual incidence to be 107.3 per 100,000 for men and 63.5 per 100,000 for women [7] which corresponds to the findings of Radhakrishnan et al., [8]. In Nigeria, Ayanniyi et al. documented that neck pain was found to be common among Nigerian university undergraduates and affects females than males [9]. Adegoke et al., and Bolanle et al., and in a separate work conducted in the South Western State of Nigeria found that the leading work-related musculoskeletal disorder was low back pain, followed by neck pain, an indication that neck pain is very prominent among musculoskeletal pain in Nigeria, but no information on cervical radiculopathy is available. [10,11]

Cervical radiculopathy primarily results from an inflammation of cervical nerve root-induced by a lesion reducing the intervertebral foramen [8]. Typical symptoms of cervical radiculopathy include pain in the cervical or periscapular region in the upper limb, as well as neurological signs such as paraesthesia, numbness, weakness and loss of reflexes in the affected nerve root distribution [12]. The aetiology of neck pain leading to cervical radiculopathy is multifactorial and poorly understood, but

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the common factors include poor posture, depression, anxiety, ageing, acute injury and occupational and sporting activities [13,14]. These lead to altered joint mechanics, muscle structure or function and can result in mechanical neck pain [15]. Peterson and Bergmann, and Gattermann stated that the most common cause of mechanical neck pain (MNP) is zygoapophyseal joint locking and muscle strain [14,16]. Although neck pain leading to cervical radiculopathy originates from a variety of spinal tissues, the cervical nerve roots are vulnerable to injury resulting from foramina impingement, disc herniation, direct spinal trauma, and foraminal stenosis [17,18,19]. The effect of compression duration is of particular relevance to nerve root injury because the nerve root can be susceptible to both sustained and transient mechanical loading, sustained nerve root loading is associated with a disc herniation and spondylosis [19], while transient loading to the root can result from sports and automotive traumas [20, 21]. Some complications accompanying cervical radiculopathy can be present as symptoms which include cervical pain aggravated by movement, referred pain (occiput, between the shoulder blades, upper limbs), retro-orbital or temporal pain (from C1 to C2), cervical stiffness—reversible or irreversible, vague numbness, tingling, or weakness in upper limbs, dizziness or vertigo, poor balance, syncope, migraine, "pseudo-angina" and, signs, i.e. poorly localized tenderness, limited range of cervical movement, minor neurological changes like inverted supinator jerks unless complicated by myelopathy. [13].

There is a significant amount of evidence available to support the use of physical therapy interventions for patients with cervical radiculopathy, and the benefit of physical therapy and manual techniques in general for patients with neck pain with or without radicular symptoms [22]. General physical therapy management of cervical radiculopathy is aimed at disease consequences such as pain, numbness, tingling and weakness in the upper extremity [23]. Various therapeutic interventions are applied to treat cervical radiculopathy like rest, moist heat, ice, cervical collar, postural education, neck exercises, strengthening exercises, Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulator (TENS), Interferential Therapy (IFT), Short Wave Diathermy (SWD), Ultra Sound (US), Electro-Muscular Stimulator (EMS), cervical traction, cervical and thoracic spine manipulation/mobilization, and neural mobilization.

Manual therapy, a component of physical therapy, has been known to supplement and contribute to other medical specialties and a few of various mobilization techniques commonly used in physiotherapy practice are Maitland, Mulligan, McKenzie, Kaltenborn, Cyriax, etc. [25].

While seeking clinical based intervention, manual therapists are commonly used in the treatment of neck and arm pain [26]. A multidisciplinary rehabilitation approach including patient education, pain control and physical therapy are the first line of treatment recommended for cervical radiculopathy patients [27]. Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides (SNAGS), a form of manual therapy, refers to a spinal physical therapy treatment technique developed by Mulligan [28]. Sustained natural apophyseal glides (SNAGS), is a form of manual therapy that involves a combination of a sustained facet glide with active motion, followed by overpressure which applies to the cervical region. SNAGS technique involves a mid to end-range facet joint mobilization manually applied anterocranially or posteroanterior along the plane of treatment within the desired joint, combined with a small amount of manual pressure or traction. The treatment aims to increase movement within the spine and decrease

symptomatic pain [28]. The technique though popular in some part of the world is not well known nor practice in Nigeria. There is also a dearth of evidence base documentation on its effect on radiating pain especially in this part of the world hence this study.

Methodology:

Subjects Patients with cervical radiculopathy referred to the Outpatient Physiotherapy Department of the Usmanu Danfodio University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto-Nigeria for physiotherapy treatment.

Inclusion Criteria The following categories of patients were recruited in this study,

1. Subjects diagnosed with neck pain of mechanical origin of not less than three months who were referred by a physician or seen on the first contact by the researcher.
2. Subjects between the age of 25 and 75 years.
3. Subjects without pathology affecting the neck and upper limb(s).

Exclusion Criteria

1. Participants with a history of vertebro-basilar artery insufficiency.
2. Patient with history of cervical surgery or arthroplasty, also
3. A participant who presents with malnutrition, fever, tumours, were excluded from the study.

Sampling Technique A purposive sampling technique was used to recruit patients for the study.

Research Design The research design was Quasi-experimental design.

$$\text{Sample size calculation } N = \frac{4(Z^2)p(1-p)}{D^2}$$

N- is the total sample size [29]

P= pre study estimate of proportion which is always 0.2,

Z= standard normal deviation (1.96)

D= total width of expected confidence interval (0.2)

$$N = \frac{4(1.96)^2 \times 0.2(1-0.2)}{(0.2)^2} = 61.5$$

A total of 67 patients were recruited to give room for attrition.

Instrument

1. Inclinometer: The 0.31kg USA made Baseline Bubble Inclinometer for cervical range of motions
2. Stadiometer: This consists of height meter and weighing scale made by Seca, United Kingdom to measure the height and bodyweight of subjects respectively, weighted 250kg.
3. Neck Pain Disability Index (NDI) Questionnaires. Neck disability was assessed using the Neck Pain Disability Index Questionnaire (NDI), which is a commonly utilized outcome measure to capture perceived disability in patients with neck pain [30]. The NDI contains ten items, seven, related to activities of daily living, two, related to pain, and one, related to concentration [31]. Each item is scored from zero to five, and the total score was expressed as a percentage, with higher scores indicating greater disability.

The NDI has demonstrated moderate test re-test reliability ($r=0.89$, $p < 0.001$) and is a valid ($r=0.70$, $p < 0.05$) health outcome measure in a patient population with cervical radiculopathy. [32]

4. Visual Analogue Scale (VAS).

Intervention Procedures Ethical Approval for this study with protocol number IPH/OAU/12/673 was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee of the Institute of Public Health of the Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife, Nigeria before the commencement of the study, and a copy was taken to Usmanu Danfodio University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto- Nigeria. Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides (SNAGS) with active arm movement: Each subject was given SNAGS on cervical vertebra with the simultaneous active mobilization of arm movement (MWM) according to [28]. Subject was in a sitting position facing the wall bar. Physiotherapist placed one thumb reinforced over the other on the spinous process of the implicated cervical vertebra, then exerted pressure on the implicated spinous process, the pressure was sustained for 60secs maximum [25,33] as the patient actively performs shoulder abduction of the affected arm with radicular pain supported on the wall bar, and subsequently lowers and rests the arm for 60 seconds [34]. On each visit, six repetitions were performed twice a week for six weeks [35]

Cryotherapy Cryotherapy- in the form of 0.5 kg ice pack was placed for 7 minutes on the posterior aspect of the neck; each subject was in a prone lying position with a pillow under the chest and the head supported by a small, rolled towel in a neutral position. The ice pack was placed from neck base (behind the ear) to supraclavicular and scapular regions for 7 minutes according to Algafly [36]

Outcome Measures Pain intensity was measured using VAS, functional neck disability was measured using Neck Disability Index Questionnaires, and cervical flexion and extension were measured using inclinometer. These Outcome Measures were applied three times, pre-treatments, 3rd and 6thweek treatments.

Data Analysis IBM version 23.0 was used to analyze the data. A p-value of 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. The data were summarized using descriptive and inferential statistics. Repeated measured ANOVA was used to compare the mean values of outcome measures pre-treatment, 3rd week and six weeks of the treatment session.

Results

PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SUBJECTS

Presented in table 1 are the mean height, weight, and BMI is 78.39 ± 14.06 m, 01.71 ± 00.08 kg, 26.85 ± 04.89 and 39.50 ± 03.38 kg/m² respectively.

Effect of SNAGS on pain intensity (PI) and neck disability index (NDI) pre-treatment, 3rd week and 6th-week outcome measures.

Presented in table 2 is ANOVA comparing the mean values of the pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th-week treatment of participants. The results revealed that there was a significant difference in the PI of pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th-week treatment ($F = 521.35$; $p < 0.001$). The results also revealed that there was a significant difference in the NDI of pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th-week treatment ($F = 102.55$; $p < 0.001$).

Table 1 Physical characteristics of the subjects (N = 67).

VARIABLES	Minimum	Maximum	Mean + SD
Age/Years	25	72	47.45+ 12.38
Ht/m	58	106.72	78.39 +14.05
Wt/Kg	1.58	1.82	1.70 + 0.07
BMI/Kgm ²	20.76	37.80	26.84+ 4.89
Keys: BMI = Body Mass Index, Ht = Height, Wt = Weight			

Table 2 Summary of Repeated measure ANOVA with Post hoc comparing the pre-treatment, 3rdweek and 6th-week treatment of PI and NDI (N=67).

Variables	Mean±SD	F	p
PI			
Pre-treatment	9.42±0.83a		
3rd week	2.29±0.91 b	521.35	.001
6th week	0.38±0.49c		
NDI			
Pre-	36.50±11.81a		
3rd week	13.46±05.89b	102.55	.001
6th week	5.04±03.46c		
Keys: Post-Hoc Tukey honestly significant difference: Superscripts a, b, c, d, e, f, g and h letters mean mode with the same superscripts indicates no significant difference between mean; mean mode with different superscripts indicate a significant difference. PI = Pain Intensity, NDI = Neck Disability Index, N = Number of participants, S.D = Standard Deviation, F = ANOVA Value and p = p-value.			

Effects of SNAGS on cervical range of motion pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th week.

Presented in table 3 is repeated measure ANOVA comparing the mean values of the pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th-week treatment of subjects. The results revealed that there was a significant increase in right flexion ($F = 16.86$; $p < 0.001$) and right rotation ($F = 31.35$; $p < 0.001$) when the pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th week of cervical range of motion in were compared.

Discussion

The specific objectives of this study were to assess the effects of sustained natural apophyseal glides (SNAGS) on the pain intensity, neck functional disability and range of motion in patients with cervical radiculopathy. A significant reduction between the pre-treatment, 3rd and 6th post-treatment pain intensity was observed in this study. Sustained natural apophyseal glides were found to produce a significant reduction in pain intensity in this study. This is by the study conducted by Nikeeta,[37]

Table 3 Summary of Repeated measure ANOVA with Post hoc comparing the pre-treatment, 3rd week and 6th week treatment ROM of SNAGS Group N= 67

Variables	Mean±SD	F	p
CROM			
Rt Side Flexion			
Pre-treatment	43.29 ±09.51a		
3rd week	44.58 ±07.21b	16.86	.001
6th week	49.17 ±05.65 c		
Rt Rotation			
Pre-	43.39 ±15.59e		
3rd week	44.79 ±11.37f	31.35	.001
6th week	56.96 ±08.25g		

Keys: Post-Hoc Tukey honestly significant difference: Superscripts a, b, c, d, e, f, g and h letters mean mode with the same superscripts indicates no significant difference between mean; mean mode with different superscripts indicate a significant difference.
Lt = Left, Rt = Right, N = Number of participants,
CROM = Cervical Range of Motion,
S.D = Standard Deviation,
F = ANOVA Value and p = p-value.

which reported that SNAGS produced instant relief in mechanical induced neck disorder with pinched nerves (radiculopathy). The reduction in pain intensity could be reduced to the fact that SNAGS produces a sympathoexcitatory effect which is instrumental to the production of analgesic response in C5/6 [38].

Abdelgalil, [39] compared and reported the effectiveness of both high-velocity low amplitude manipulation and sustained apophyseal glides on pain and range of motion in patients with mechanical neck pain, the instant reduction observed was deduced from the instant release of nociceptive as suggested by Melzack and Wall [40]. A significant neck disability reduction was also observed as a result of SNAGS intervention in this study, this is in consonant with result presented by Kumar, [41] where he concluded that SNAGS was a useful manual therapy technique for achieving faster result as measured in terms of ROM, NDI and pain at available end ranges in neck disorders compared with other conservative physiotherapy techniques. Patient's neck resistance to posterior-anterior pressures resulted in significant improvement in disability, pain, and isometric neck muscle strength in different directions Thomas [42].

SNAGS reduces PI significantly at 6th week of intervention since SNAGS produces instant analgesic effect due to pain gate theory Mendell [43]. The gate control theory of pain, proposed by Melzack and Wall stated that spinal nociceptive transmission neurons receive inputs from low threshold mechanoreceptors, but this input is gated by feed-forward activation of inhibitory neurons located in the substantial gelatinosa of the dorsal horn [40]. In a related study, Ali et al., [44] found that patients with

non-specific neck pain treated with SNAGS manual physical therapy techniques and followed by intermittent electrical cervical traction were more effective in reduction of pain and enhancement of function, as compared to those patients treated with SNAGS manual physical therapy techniques alone.

Sustained natural apophyseal glides were found to reduce the cervical range of motion significantly in our study. Manipulative therapy which includes SNAGS was reported to alter segmental biomechanics by releasing trapped meniscoids, break down adhesions, or by abolished distortion in the intervertebral disc [45, 46] and restored component movement which invariably increases the mobility of the region [33]. Also, individual motion segments are thought capable of buckling, thereby producing relatively large vertebral motions that achieve a new position of stable equilibrium [47]. The manipulative impulse provides sufficient energy to restore a buckled segment to a lower energy level, thus reducing mechanical stress or strain on soft and hard spinal tissues [48].

In the range of motion of patients with cervical radiculopathy, flexion to a side may precipitate pain due to the compression of the structures on the side which decompresses the other side. In our study, most of the patients reported pain on the right side indicating right radicular pain. Our results indicated that such pressure resulting in the pain was relieved by SNAGS; hence there was an increase in ROM of both rotation and flexion to the right.

It was also observed that both males and females are equally affected in this study, as there were 12 females and 12 males participated in the study this is in contrary to the findings of Barret et al., [7] and Ayanniyi et al., [9] where more males were affected than females, reason could be due to the fact that women in the domain of the study are physically active and overweight. It was observed that males are not too involved in rigorous and risky activities in the domain of study that can precipitate neck pain compared to the population study of Ayanniyi et al., [9].

Conclusion

The study established that Sustained Natural Apophyseal Glides is effective in reducing the pain intensity, increase the range of motion and improving the neck ability of patients with cervical radiculopathy.

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